

Understanding Lawyer's Burnout: The Intersection of Perfectionism, Ethical Preferences, and Self-compassion Strategies

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The study explored the predictive role of age, perfectionism, self-compassion, and ethical preferences in relation to burnout among lawyers. The sample consisted of 70 lawyers with an experience of 7 years or more in practice. Non-probability sampling techniques were used to generate the sample of participants. Further, statistical analysis of the data was made using the software SPSS, including descriptive statistics, correlational analysis, and linear regression. Contrary to the hypothesis, low levels of burnout and low scores in the respective dimensions (emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, & reduced personal accomplishment) were seen among the participants. Although age was not significantly predictive of burnout, a positive correlation between perfectionism and burnout was established, indicating that lawyers with more perfectionism are likely to suffer from increased burnout. Though not statistically significant, self-compassion and ethical preferences were found to negatively correlate with burnout, suggesting that the absence of self-compassion and adherence to ethical principles may mitigate burnout risk. Hence, it is suggested that a further study should be conducted, involving a larger sample size, for a stronger basis for the correlations established. In all, the overall results establish the need to focus on improving perfectionism as well as developing self-compassion and ethical integrity in order to prevent legal professionals from burnout.

Keywords: Burnout, perfectionism, self-compassion, ethical preferences, lawyers

The legal profession is one of the most demanding work contexts, resulting in lawyers being susceptible to high stress levels or even burnout. Burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a diminished sense of personal accomplishment, and is now somewhat of an epidemic in the legal world. Studies have shown that lawyers who exhibit perfectionistic tendencies are more susceptible to experiencing chronic stress (Hewitt et al., 2003) because they often neglect their well-being, leading to increased levels of burnout (Maslach & Leiter, 2005). Lawyers with a firm adherence to their ethical principles might not feel so much stress and burnout due to the integrity they place on their professional conduct. Studies have shown that lawyers who cultivate self-compassion are better equipped to cope with the pressures of legal practice and experience greater resilience in the face of adversity (Allen & Leary, 2010).

Understanding Perfectionism

Each brush stroke conspicuously impressed by the artist; an assignment dutifully perfected by a student; an unsatisfied craving for flawlessness, a synonym for perfectionism, a trait that permeates

various aspects of human endeavor, from creative pursuits to academic achievements. Perfectionism is a characteristic of one's personality, defined as "striving for flawlessness and setting exceedingly high standards for performance, accompanied by tendencies for overly critical evaluations" (Stoeber, 2011). Perfectionism is when a person "demands of oneself or others a higher quality of performance than is required by the situation" (Hollender, 1965) thus resulting in a self-critical behavior, prone to negative judgments (Frost et al., 1990). The perfectionist applies extremely high standards for himself while being overly critical of himself (Curran & Hill, 2019).

Perfectionism comes in different forms, yet researchers have focused on the following two established dimensions: perfectionistic strivings and perfectionistic concerns (Stoeber & Gaudreau, 2017). Perfectionistic strivings, also called personal standards perfectionism, indicate an individual's internal tendency toward perfection and exceptionally high personal performance standards, moderately related to positive outcomes, like academic achievement (Madigan, 2019). Perfectionistic concerns, also called evaluative concerns perfectionism, reflect worries about making mistakes, apprehension regarding negative social judgment if not perfect, uncertainties about one's actions, feelings of discrepancy between one's lofty standards and actual performance, adverse reactions to imperfection (Stoeber & Otto, 2006) and dissatisfaction with achievements (Bieling et al., 2004; Frost et al., 1993; Stoeber, 2018).

Hamachek (1978) introduced the concept of "normal perfectionism" to describe the healthier form of perfectionism, contrasting it with the maladaptive form termed "neurotic perfectionism". Maladaptive perfectionism involves negative reinforcement and self-defeating behaviors (Slade & Owens, 1998) like concerns about external evaluation, self-doubt, and fear of

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making mistakes. However, some aspects of perfectionism might be adaptive because they aim for flawlessness and a sense of excellence, striving to achieve their goals (Hamachek, 1978). Healthy perfectionism is related to positive outcomes where high standards and their attainment provide rewards without psychological distress.

Burnout

Burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by (feeling of diminished energy and reluctance to perform tasks), depersonalization (the feeling of dehumanizing others, indifference, & lack of connection), and reduced personal accomplishment (lack of fulfillment from personal achievements one feels incompetent to do; Maslach & Leiter, 2016) that may manifest in individuals who work with people in some capacity (Maslach & Jackson, 1981a, 1981b, 1984a, 1986).

Typically, burnout is not purely an individual factor but is rather a result of specific work-environment conditions. It can be seen as a reduction in motivation and performance, as well as a factor in various psychological problems. Burnout is usually perceived as a state of physical and mental exhaustion, disengagement, dissatisfaction, cynicism toward oneself and others, and is thus often a product of prolonged and unrelieved stress (Kristensen et al., 2005).

In the case of lawyers, burnout may have detrimental effects on their work performance (Chlap & Brown, 2022). It is believed that high levels of occupational stress correlate with widespread burnout on both a personal and work-level among lawyers (Tsai et al., 2009). The diathesis-stress model suggests that certain predisposition factors increase the possibility of developing depression or burnout when an individual is confronted with high anxiety and stress, with one such factor being perfectionism (Ingram & Luxton, 2005). In the legal field, professionals engage in frequent client interactions, conduct intricate analyses of complex legal matters, and face significant decision-making responsibilities and psychological demands, resulting in heightened pressure and stress for those practicing law (Platsidou & Salman, 2012). Burnout has also been identified as a primary cause of attorney turnover (Maslach & Leiter, 2016).

Perfectionism, which usually requires great attention to detail, is highly critical among lawyers because their job requirements highly demand it. They are always expected to be a step ahead in foreseeing potential problems and having alternative arguments. However, this continuous pursuit of perfection could result in feelings of inadequacy and excessive self-blame when things do not go so well as envisaged. A trained lawyer anticipates and prevents any issues that may arise, which motivates him to be careful and perceive even minor threats as hugely serious (Gordon, 2015).

Age is a possible factor that has some influence on burnout in employees. Some research indicates that younger professionals may have increased levels of burnout because they lack experience and have less secure employment positions, making it difficult for them to cope with the stressors that they face at work (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). However, other studies even confess that the elderly are victims of burnout because of the long period during which they have been experiencing occupational stress, progressively decreasing adaptability, and cumulative dissatisfaction with their jobs over the years (Schaufeli et al., 2009). As per social exchange theory, burnout

is the result when employees feel that there is an imbalance in their inputs and outputs in the work environment (Schaufeli et al., 2011). This eventually lends itself to burnout because they tend to spend emotionally exhausting days. Thus, depersonalization or dehumanization refers to a stress coping mechanism that may lead to low levels of personal fulfillment. In eliminating the contribution to the model about personal fulfillment, organizational theory suggests that work overload and role uncertainty may eventuate burnout, as these are the primary risk factors of burnout (Schaufeli et al., 2011; Golembiewski et al., 1983). The low level of personal fulfillment of an individual at the place of work, coupled with emotional tiredness, will encompass a person into burnout syndrome.

Ethical Thinking/ Preferences

The ethical norm governing professional behavior lays down certain rules that are intended to guide appropriate conduct in the daily practice of the law. Lawyers are usually perfectionistic and clergy-like in their determination to avoid mistakes, but the subject of ethicality in their practice looms large. These unethical practices can, in turn, traumatize the very same lawyers, heightening feelings of stress and guilt. Thus, having professional duties in conflict with personal morals is a firm source of burnout from within. According to Parker, lawyers generally gravitate towards four ethical paradigms: Zealous Advocacy (to fulfill the desires of clients), Responsible Lawyering (concerning the letter of the law), Moral Activism (considering social change), and the Ethic of Care (offering protection to people without regard to law; Evans & Forgasz, 2013). To some extent, these four categories determine how lawyers will respond to professional conduct and ethical dilemmas and make decisions in various contexts.

Law is an area of profession that deals with frequent contact with clients and rigorous analysis of legal issues (Tsai et al., 2009). A propensity for an intense focus upon delicate particulars, together with anticipating counter-arguments, may give way to excessive caution, self-blame, and stress, interfering with those inherent challenges to which a lawyer may find themselves faced while practicing such ethical paradigms that could inhibit being right or being true to one's clients and thus might be contributing to burnout (Schaufeli et al., 2009).

Self-compassion

Self-compassion, as a general term, means comfort instead of criticism of oneself in adverse conditions. The content is based on self-compassion as a positive mindset as well as a good self-relation (Neff, 2003a; Neff, 2003b). Neff (2011) claims that self-compassion is legitimately aligned to greater well-being measured in terms of lower scores in depression, less anxiety, and increased satisfaction in life (MacBeth & Gumley, 2012). Self-compassion has three elements that are intertwined and mutually affecting: Self-kindness (the compassion with which one treats oneself) versus self-judgment, sense of common humanity (everyone makes mistakes, fails, & feels inadequate) versus isolation, and mindfulness (in the moment) versus over-identification (Gilbert, 2009). Within this environment where the majority of lawyers are isolated from one another, self-care and understanding thereby allow lawyers to adjust harsh self-judgments and perfectionism that might cause burnout (Neff & Germer, 2013; Raab, 2014)

This humane provision for imperfection, complemented by

mindfulness, enables lawyers to form a more realistic position on things, reducing feelings of isolation and being overwhelmed. In the end, the incorporation of self-compassion into the legal profession would definitely contribute to enhanced well-being, which would translate to reduced stress and increased well-being (Krasner et al., 2009).

Rationale of the Study

Burnout has become common, especially among people-oriented professions, but lawyers seem to fall victim with their kind of work because it is highly emotive. Burnout has been characterized by high emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a diminished personal accomplishment; hence, it is an important concern for any group of legal professionals (Maslach & Leiter, 2016). Perfectionism—the setting of excessively high standards and perhaps overly critical self-evaluations has become one of the most significant predictors of burnout among lawyers (Curran & Hill, 2019). Perfectionism drives people towards excellence. At the same time, the fear of failure and the tendency toward self-criticism have many negative aspects that cause people to experience chronic stress or fatigue related to emotions (Stoeber, 2011; Hewitt et al., 2003). Perplexing lawyers are not up to standard; on the contrary, they undergo stress from ethical dilemmas, as perfectionism in most cases constrains them from fulfilling their ethical obligations (Freedman & Smith, 2009). Resolving both ends of that particular continuum is necessary to reduce burnout and improve the wellness of legal professionals. Self-compassion, which promotes compassionate and accepting attitudes towards oneself, has proven to be a buffer against burnout (Allen & Leary, 2010; Neff & Germer, 2013). Self-compassion shields lawyers from the pernicious consequences of their perfectionism and makes them better equipped to gain resilience and coping strategies against the negative consequences caused by perfectionism.

This study intends to investigate the relationship between perfectionism, ethical preferences, and self-compassion with burnout in lawyers. It aims to investigate if self-compassion functions as a moderator between perfectionism, ethical stressors, and adverse effects on lawyers' well-being.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess burnout in lawyers.
- To assess the relationship between age and burnout in lawyers
- To assess the relationship between perfectionism, self-compassion, ethical preferences, and burnout among lawyers
- To understand the causal relationship of age, perfectionism, self-compassion and ethical preferences with burnout among lawyers.

Hypotheses of the Study

- There will be significant levels of burnout experienced by lawyers.
- There will be a significant relationship between age and burnout.
- ○ There will be a significant positive correlation between perfectionism and burnout.
- There will be a significant positive correlation between ethical preferences and burnout.
- There will be a significant negative correlation between self-compassion and burnout.
- There will be a significant causal relationship between age,

perfectionism, self-compassion, and ethical preferences in the prediction of burnout.

Method

Participants

The study consisted of a sample of 70 lawyers, out of which 47 (67.1%) are males, whereas 23 (32.9%) are females. These lawyers have practiced for an average period of 7 years. 15 (21.4%) among them were found to have experiences ranging from 7-10 years, 17 (24.3%) had a time of practice from 10 to 15 years, while 15 (21.4%) had between 15 and 20 years, with the remaining 23 (32.9%) having more than 20 years. For the study, purposive sampling and convenience sampling non-probability sampling methods were used.

Inclusion Criteria

This research included lawyers with a minimum of 7 years in practice. Lawyers with less than 7 years of experience were not considered for the study, as the very initial 5-7 years are considered the honeymoon period, and probably because burnout is much likely to be lower in this period, hence irrelevant in the study.

Research Design

The research design employed in the study was a quantitative research design. Pearson's product-moment correlation was used to investigate the extent and direction of relationships among the study variables. Linear regression analysis was done to examine the causal relationships of predictor variables (age, perfectionism, self-compassion, & ethical preferences) on the criterion variable (burnout).

Measures

Big Three Perfectionism Scale-Short Form: The Big Three Perfectionism Scale (BTPS), introduced by Smith et al. (2016) consists of 16 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) and assesses the three dimensions of perfectionism. Rigid perfectionism attempts to attain a flawless performance and associates self-worth with meeting high personal standards, including self-oriented perfectionism and self-worth contingencies. Self-critical perfectionism, as pointed out by Dunkley et al. (2003) emphasizes worries about mistakes, uncertainty concerning actions, harsh self-criticism, and the belief that others require perfection. Narcissistic perfectionism includes attributes such as other-oriented perfectionism, hypercriticism, entitlement, and grandiosity, and is characterized by arrogance along with unrealistic expectations from others. The Cronbach's alpha ranged between .83 to .90 for the 10 facets and .92 to .93 for the three global factors (Smith et al., 2016).

Maslach Burnout Inventory: Maslach Burnout Inventory, 3rd edition (Maslach et al., 1996) is one of the most commonly used tools for self-assessment of burnout risk. It underlines three components of burnout: exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal achievement. Section A, Exhaustion/Burnout, is composed of 7 items that assess bodily manifestations, chronic fatigue, sleeplessness, and exhaustion due to work. A score of 30 indicates a high risk of severe burnout, while scores below 7 indicate low risk. Section B, Depersonalization or loss of empathy, also has seven items about "dehumanized" interpersonal relationships, with scores over 12 being characteristic of severe burnout. Section C, Personal

Achievement, is composed of eight items, which indicate how the individual perceives their sense of competence and success regarding their work. Burnout was defined as high if a person scored less than or equal to 33 in this area and low if they scored greater than or equal to 40. Reliability coefficients of the MBI range from Cronbach Alpha .71 to .90 and one-month test-retest .60 to .80. Convergent validity coefficients range from .20 to .56 (Coker & Omoluabi, 2009).

Self-compassion Scale-Short: The self-reporting tool, Self-Compassion Scale (Neff, 2003a) comprises 26 items designed to diagnose the way a person perceives self-compassion. The three major areas being assessed through this tool are self-compassion, shared humanity, and mindfulness, along with their converse meanings, which are self-judgment, isolation, and over-identification. The more concise 12-item version that underscored this study gauges how often people would respond to experiences of not being good enough with what they think, feel, and how they act. The scale displays good retest stability (0.93) and internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.90$; Neff, 2003a). It is also shown to have convergent validity and is associated with ratings of self-compassion by romantic partners and therapists, and predicts the extent of self-compassionate thinking (Leary et al., 2007). This shorter form is preferred because it gives a good estimate of total self-compassion rather than depending on less reliable subscale scores.

Ethical Preferences for Lawyers: The Ethical Preferences for Lawyers scale aids lawyers in assessing their ethical reasoning. Developed by Parker (2004) it contains four ethical preferences: Responsible Lawyering (RL), Relationships of Care (RoC), Zealous Advocacy (ZA), and Moral Activism (MA). This 6-point Likert scale, with 1 being "strongly agree" and 6 being "strongly disagree," provides valuable insight for lawyers regarding the underlying ethical goals that inform their professional actions without having to assess understanding of particular legal conduct or ethical dilemmas. The EPL scale has demonstrated fairly good internal consistency ($\alpha = .76-.88$) across its subscales (Evans, 2010). Its construct validity has been supported through correlations with established ethical decision-making frameworks (Parker, 2004).

Procedure

The appropriate standardised scales were selected for assessing the study variables. Following a pilot study, data were collected through a Google form. Along with the data, the informed consent and demographic details form were attached to the Google form. It ensured that only those eligible participants, that is, the lawyers with a minimum of 7 years in practice, would fill the form. The collected data was transferred to a Google spreadsheet, and then the raw data was rigorously scrutinised. Analysis of data was undertaken using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics measures of mean and standard deviation of all the variables were calculated. Further, Pearson's product-moment coefficient of correlation was used to generate a correlation matrix to establish the correlation between all the variables. Further, to study the causal relation of the predictor variables (age, perfectionism, self-compassion, & ethical preferences) on the criterion variable (burnout), the linear regression method was adopted.

Ethical Considerations

The following ethical considerations were kept in mind during the conduct of the present study.

- Informed consent was taken from each of the participants.
- Confidentiality was maintained. The participants were informed that their responses would be used only for academic purposes.
- The participation in the study was completely voluntary. The participants had the right to withdraw at any point in the study.
- The feedback from the study will be shared with the participants post-completion.

Results

Table 1

Mean and Standard Deviation of Three Dimensions of Burnout Measured by MBI

Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation
Exhaustion	8.32	5.85
Depersonalisation	6.84	6.73
Personal Achievement	37.14	9.41

Note. $N=70$

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation for the three burnout dimensions, as measured by the Maslach Burnout Inventory, among 70 participants. For exhaustion, the mean is 8.32 ($SD = 5.85$); for depersonalization, the mean is 6.84 ($SD = 6.73$); and for personal accomplishment, the mean is 37.14 ($SD = 9.41$).

Table 2

Mean and Standard Deviation for Lawyers on Age Perfectionism, Burnout, Self-compassion, and Ethical Preferences

Dimensions	Mean	Standard Deviation
Burnout	52.31	11.972
Age	42.57	9.118
Perfectionism	46.16	10.159
Self-Compassion	39.26	8.235
Ethical Preferences	49.36	12.717

Note. $N=70$

Table 2 presents the mean scores for Burnout (52.31), Age (42.57), Perfectionism (46.16), Self-Compassion (39.26), and Ethical Preferences (49.36), which reflect the average levels in the sample. The standard deviations indicate variability among participants: Burnout, 11.97; Age, 9.12; Perfectionism, 10.16; Self-Compassion, 8.24; Ethical Preferences, 12.72.

Table 3a denotes Pearson's product-moment correlations among Burnout, Age, Perfectionism, Self-Compassion, and Ethical Preferences. A significant positive correlation was observed between perfectionism and burnout ($r = 0.320, p < 0.01$), and between age and self-compassion ($r = 0.253, p < 0.05$), indicating that older respondents tend to be more self-compassionate. Self-Compassion also tended to be negatively correlated with Perfectionism ($r = -0.195$) and Burnout ($r = -0.016$), although these relationships were not statistically significant. Age was negatively correlated with ethical preferences ($r = -0.096, p < 0.05$), and ethical preferences were negatively correlated with both perfectionism ($r = -0.232$) and burnout ($r = -0.153$) as well, but not significantly.

Table 3a*Correlation Matrix for Age, Perfectionism, Burnout, Self-compassion, and Ethical Preferences*

	Burnout	Age	Perfectionism	Self-compassion	Ethical Preferences
Burnout	1.000	-0.038	0.320**	-0.016	-0.153
Age		1.000	0.045	0.253*	-0.096
Perfectionism			1.000	-0.195	-0.232
Self-Compassion				1.000	0.018
Ethical Preferences					1.000

Note. $N=70$. $a p < .05$ (*). $b p < .01$ (**)

Table 3b

Correlation Matrix for Age, Perfectionism, Self-compassion, Ethical Preferences, and Dimensions of Burnout- Emotional Exhaustion, Depersonalisation, and Reduced Personal Accomplishment

	Age	P	SC	EP	EE	D	PA
Age	1.000	0.045	0.253*	-0.096	-0.199	-0.258*	0.260*
P		1.000	-0.195	-0.232	0.343**	0.296*	-0.019
SC			1.000	0.018	-0.201	-0.250*	0.284
EP				1.000	-0.026	0.325**	-0.411**
EE					1.000	0.567**	-0.191
D						1.000	-0.383**
PA							1.000

Note. $N=70$ P= Perfectionism, SC= Self Compassion, EP= Ethical Preferences, EE= Emotional Exhaustion, D= Depersonalisation, PA= Personal Achievement $a p < .05$ (*). $b p < .01$ (**)

Table 3b displays the results of Pearson's correlation between Age, Perfectionism, Self-Compassion, Ethical Preferences, and the three dimensions of burnout emotional exhaustion, Depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment, within the studied sample. The results indicate that while there is a statistically significant positive correlation between age and reduced personal accomplishment ($r = 0.260, p < 0.05$), a statistically significant negative correlation exists between age and depersonalization ($r = -0.258, p < 0.05$). Though not statistically significant, there exists a negative correlation between age and emotional exhaustion ($r = -0.199$). Perfectionism is found to have a statistically significant

positive correlation with emotional exhaustion ($r = 0.343, p < 0.01$) and depersonalisation ($r = 0.296, p < 0.05$). Though not statistically significant, there is a negative correlation between perfectionism and reduced personal accomplishment ($r = -0.019$).

Depersonalisation is found to have a statistically significant positive correlation with self-compassion ($r = -0.250, p < 0.05$), and a statistically significant positive correlation with ethical preferences ($r = 0.325, p < 0.01$). There is a statistically significant negative correlation between ethical preferences and reduced personal accomplishment ($r = -0.411, p < 0.01$).

Table 4*Predictors of Burnout*

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable = Burnout				
	Beta	Simple r	t	R Square	Adjusted R Square
Perfectionism	.316*	.320*	2.574	.116	.062

Note. $p < 0.05$

Table 4 demonstrates the results of the linear regression analysis, detailing the estimated effects of the predictor variable- Perfectionism on the dependent variable- Burnout. Among the predictors, Perfectionism emerges as a significant predictor of Burnout ($B = 0.320, p < 0.01$), suggesting that higher levels of perfectionism are associated with increased levels of Burnout. The R-square value of 0.102 means that approximately 10.2% of the variability in the dependent variable, Burnout, is explained by the

independent variable, i.e., Perfectionism. Basically, it explains that 10.2% of the variation in the outcome variable can be attributed to the independent variable - perfectionism, while the remaining variability is unexplained.

Discussion

The purpose of the research was to explore how age, perfectionism, self-compassion, and ethical preferences served in the

predictive challenge of burnout among lawyers with a minimum of seven years in practice. A survey method was used to employ purposive and convenience sampling to collect data from 70 subjects (M: $F=60:40$). The findings were analyzed by SPSS software, i.e., descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and linear regression were applied to explore the relationship between variables.

It was found that the level of burnout was relatively low for lawyers in the study. Table 1 indicates the mean scores for emotional exhaustion (8.32) and depersonalization (6.84), and personal achievement of 37.14, indicating that burnout levels for the existing sample were not as severe as expected, and came out in low or moderate categories. High levels of exhaustion are a key component of burnout and can lead to negative outcomes such as reduced job performance and emotional well-being (Maslach & Jackson, 1981a), which contradicts the hypothesis that a significant amount of burnout would be experienced. This might be attributed to the small sample size and the possibility that the Maslach Burnout Inventory, used to measure burnout, may not capture the specific nuances of burnout in legal professionals.

It has been hypothesised in the study that there is a significant relationship between age and burnout. As shown in Table 3a, there is a negative correlation ($r=-0.038$) between age and burnout, although not statistically significant, implying that burnout tends to decrease among lawyers as they age. Burnout has been found to diminish with age (Ahola et al., 2008) in human services workers. The results presented in Table 3b indicate a negative correlation ($r=-0.199$) between age and emotional exhaustion. This suggests that older individuals may be less emotionally exhausted than their younger counterparts due to the possibility that they have improved coping mechanisms over time (Bianchi et al., 2015). Another aspect of burnout, depersonalization, has a statistically significant negative connection ($r=-0.258$) with age. According to the research, older people may be less detached or cynical about their jobs or clients, perhaps as a result of greater emotional maturity or professional experience (Maslach et al., 2001). Results have shown that age and reduced personal accomplishment are positively correlated ($r=0.260$), suggesting that as individuals age, they may experience a decrease in their sense of personal achievement at work due to career stagnation or impending retirement (Ng & Feldman, 2010). While older workers may have better ways of coping, on the other hand, they may have reached a period of stagnation pertaining to their roles, so that there is no overall significant relationship (Enzmann et al., 1998).

It was confirmed by this study that perfectionism was the most potent predictor of burnout, thereby supporting the hypothesis that high levels of perfectionism are associated with increased levels of burnout. A significant positive correlation of perfectionism to burnout ($r = 0.320, p < 0.01$) was found, suggesting the impact of perfectionism on emotional exhaustion and burnout (Stoeber & Otto, 2006). Perfectionists set unrealistically high standards for self-evaluation, leading to chronic stress and internalized feelings of failure as a pathway to burnout. Additionally, results Table 3b indicate that individuals with higher levels of perfectionism may be more prone to experiencing emotional exhaustion in their work, as a significant positive correlation was observed between the two variables ($r = 0.343, p < 0.01$). The results also suggest that perfectionism may be associated with higher levels of cynicism or detachment ($r = 0.296$) towards others in the workplace, leading to interpersonal difficulties, focusing more on flaws or shortcomings of

others (Flett et al., 2016). Though not statistically significant, there is a negative correlation ($r=-0.019$) between perfectionism and reduced personal accomplishment, suggesting that as levels of perfectionism increase, there tends to be a decrease in the individual's sense of personal achievement or accomplishment at work and they may be more prone to feeling dissatisfied or unfulfilled with their own performance. Thus, the findings support the hypotheses that there exists a significant positive correlation between perfectionism and burnout.

Table 4 represented the linear regression analysis, which showed that the relationship between Perfectionism and Burnout is statistically significant ($B=0.316$) at a 0.01 level. The results revealed that perfectionism accounted for 11.6% of the variance in burnout scores ($R^2 = 0.116$), a highly significant finding with $F, p < 0.01$, confirming the hypothesis that perfectionism is a significant predictor of burnout. Furthermore, previous studies support these findings, showing that perfectionism contributes to chronic stress and unattainable self-imposed standards (Curran & Hill, 2016) which aggravate emotional exhaustion and burnout. Consequently, it can be concluded that higher levels of perfectionism are associated with increased burnout among the participants in this study.

The study also hypothesised (3b) that there would be a significant positive correlation between ethical preferences and burnout, which was not supported by the findings. The result denoted a negative correlation ($r=-0.153$) between ethical preferences and burnout, suggesting that lawyers' increased ethical preferences lead to lower levels of burnout. This finding supports research showing that engaging in ethical behavior can enhance well-being and resilience, thus helping to buffer against burnout (Ford & Richardson, 1994). Ethical preferences might equip individuals to work through ethical dilemmas more effectively, thus decreasing the odds that they would suffer from moral distress that, in turn, triggers burnout. Hence, the hypothesis was not proved true, though research with a larger sample may show a significant correlation between ethical preferences and burnout. Individuals experiencing burnout may adopt rigid adherence to rules or standards as a coping mechanism (Ahola & Hakanen, 2007). As can be inferred from Table 3b, lawyers with stronger ethical values may experience lower levels of personal achievement at work, leading to feelings of disillusionment or inadequacy (Kish-Gephart et al., 2010). Engaging in work that aligns with one's ethical beliefs can provide a sense of meaning and fulfillment, which may serve as a protective factor against burnout. Self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000) suggests that alignment with personal values promotes intrinsic motivation and well-being, potentially buffering against burnout.

In the study, it was hypothesised (3c) that there would be a significant negative correlation between self-compassion and burnout. As can be seen from the results in Table 3a, a negative ($r=-0.016$) but not statistically significant correlation was seen, suggesting that the more compassionate lawyers are towards themselves, lesser the burnout they will face. This result highlights the protective role of self-compassion in mitigating the negative effects of stress and promoting well-being (Neff & Germer, 2013). Self-compassion fosters emotional resilience and reduces emotional exhaustion (Neff & Germer, 2013; Krieger et al., 2016) indicating a protective effect against burnout. This suggests that self-compassion may help lawyers manage the emotional demands of their profession, thereby reducing burnout risk. More self-compassionate people have a tendency to be less perfectionistic and are better able to

handle stress, which lowers their risk of burnout (Bluth et al., 2015).

The negative correlation between age and ethical preferences ($r = -0.096$), though not statistically significant, suggests that older legal professionals may demonstrate lower levels of ethical preferences. On the contrary, ethical decision-making may improve with age and experience (Padmanabhan et al., 2016). This contradiction can be attributed to a small sample; therefore, further research with a larger and more diverse sample may establish an appropriate significant correlation. Furthermore, the negative correlation between ethical preferences and burnout ($r = -0.153$), though not statistically significant, suggests that ethical considerations might play a role in mitigating burnout risk as ethical values and integrity play an important role in promoting well-being and resilience in high-stress professions (Hamric et al., 2012).

Conclusion

The study highlights the relationships of perfectionism, self-compassion, ethical preferences, and burnout among lawyers with at least 7 years of experience. The study indicated that lawyers endure moderate levels of burnout, with a significant positive correlation between perfectionism and burnout, suggesting that lawyers with greater perfectionism are more susceptible to burnout. In contrast, a negative correlation was found between ethical preferences and burnout, indicating that lawyers with a stronger ethical stance experience lower levels of burnout. Even though the correlation between self-compassion and burnout was not statistically significant, the weak negative trend further indicates that self-compassion might mediate burnout.

Implications of the Study

This study elaborates that perfectionism is an essential factor contributing to lawyers' experiences of burnout, while ethical preferences and self-compassion serve as potential buffers. Lawyers should engage in self-reflection to foster healthy coping skills. Legal environments should emphasize work-life balance, maintaining ethical frameworks, and appropriate workloads. Early screening and intervention from mental health practitioners targeted toward perfectionism, coupled with a focus on self-compassion, would further the wellness of lawyers and reduce the manifestation of burnout in the profession.

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

The small sample size limits the generalizability of results found from this study, rendering any gender comparison on burnout unfeasible. Furthermore, the differences between different branches of law (e.g., criminal, corporate) were not explored. The Maslach Burnout Inventory, designed for helping professions, may not be the most apt to evaluate their level of burnout, while a tool that assesses the peculiarities of legal professionals would render better results.

Future research should prioritize larger, more representative samples that could allow for gender comparisons, practice area factors, and mediating or moderating models for a deeper analysis. Following that, further research should develop and validate a burnout assessment intended specifically for lawyers' experiences, involving rigorous testing on a sizable and diverse standardization sample to guarantee its reliability and validity.

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